

Project	Risk_ID	Risk	Creation Date	Occurrence Probability	Impact	Team Member	Category	Priority	Status	Action	Sprint	Backlog Item
TG	C01	Customer participation lack	01/03/2022	Average	Average	Jack	Client	Average	Open	Convince the client to participate in the project	Sprint 1	BI03
TG	E06	Team unfamiliar with the tools	01/03/2022	Low	High	Paul	Execution	Average	Monitored	Hold a workshop to train the team.	Sprint 1	BI02
TG	ER5	Requirements not properly identified	01/03/2022	Low	High	Paul	Scope and Requirement	Average	Close	hold a round of brainstorming to elect the requirements again	Sprint 1	BI01
TG	E01	Inadequately trained team.	01/03/2022	Low	High	Paul	Execution	Average	Monitored	Hold a workshop to train the team.	Sprint 1	BI02